

IMAGE VARIATIONS SUBJECTED TO VARYING LIGHT INTENSITY ON POLISHED AND UNPOLISHED ALUMINUM AND STEEL

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Abstract

Light intensity plays key role in image acquisition when image to be acquired is related to dimensional analysis then it is of great interest that how much of the variation is caused by changing light intensity, also of value is the fact that how different material and their polished or unpolished state may become the cause for variation in image. This paper discusses/ compares the variation in pixel in static images caused by light intensity variation on polished/unpolished steel and aluminum.

INTRODUCTION

Image processing is used for multiple reasons, it may be used for dimensional analysis, color variation detection, object temperature detection, fluid level detection, objects motion detection, object recognition and etc, all of these application for image processing will require to have image being acquired in the controlled environment, Light source modules play a crucial role in capturing accurate images of reflective metallic surfaces. [1] Surface inspection using machine vision techniques has seen significant progress in fields like leather defect detection. [2] Automated optical inspection techniques have proven useful for quality monitoring in the electronics industry. [3]

There are multiple factors that may affect image acquisition they may include angle of camera, objects surface, object's texture, light intensity, type of light source mono chromatic, coherent/non coherent, frequency range of light source being used, distance of object from camera and light source, UV, Vis, and IR imaging could be used as crucial non-contact sensing tools for complex material surfaces. Underwater imaging shows how lighting intensity and turbidity impact surface clarity and defect detection. [5] Digital correlation and optical image methods are used for surface analysis in harsh lighting. [6] Laser is also very much preferred but Laser speckle pattern changes

with surface roughness and machining processes [7] [1].

Improving efforts in result may include CW and UV laser polishing improves uniformity, reducing reflection inconsistency. [8] reduction of ambient light as IR interference from solar radiation introduces error in optical measurements [9], thermoelectric materials used in optical devices must be optimized for light absorption. [13] if working is related to motion, then micromotion detection with IR requires managing light scatter and angle. [11] [2] Effected image by the factors mentioned above means that when image is taken of the same object in two different environments acquired image will have significant amount of variation in location of pixels or variation in pixel values intensities, which may not

harm essence of image in most of the applications but for some of the applications it may prove to generate error which are needed to be dealt with, some of these application may include 3D Scanning of image, Precision Dimensional Analysis, Color and Texture analysis etc.

So out of all the factors that may affect image being acquired this study will be focusing on type of material which are polished and unpolished steel and aluminum, tested under variable light intensities, our goal in this study is to differentiate between how these 4 test objects behave when subjected to 4 different light sources which are reddish/pink, blue, white and warm light which are commonly used for machine vision.

Figure: 1a Blue Light

Figure: 1c Reddish/Pink Light

Figure: 1b Warm Light

Figure: 1d White Light

Figure 1: This shows test objects Polished Aluminum and Steel right and left respectively placed side by side.

In figure 1 we have placed two test objects for the purpose of comparison of their images plus in images it could be seen that at the back of these test objects there is a LUX sensor which is used to measure the light intensities from the sources being used.

Capturing images for dimensional analysis is done by 16 Mega Pixel camera of other devices which could have been used are Colorimetric sensors which rely on reflected light differences for material detection [14], IR thermopile arrays which are sensitive to temperature and surface state—crucial for real-time feedback [16] [3] CMOS-compatible thermopile arrays provide detailed temperature-dependent optical data. [18] but as our aim is not related to acquisition of

thermal profile of object therefore using simple camera was preferred. Polished surfaces is always more challenging that capturing images of an unpolished surfaces, and also type of material also affects the image being acquired as discussed previously so for this purpose this experiment is designed to analyze light intensity variations along with two different materials and their surface being polished and unpolished further detail of the experimental setup is discussed in next section.

Materials & Methods

This study comprises of experiments which are conducted to determine image variations when test

object is subjected to varying light intensities, and major focus is on how images of different test object behave in varying light intensities. Test object involved here are incline as shown in figure 2 made

from Aluminum and Steel in Polished and Unpolished state.

Figure 2a : Side View

Figure 2b: Front View

Figure 2 Shows test object which was used in these experiments from its front and side view w.r.t light source and camera.

of images included keeping camera being stationary, ambient light, same edge detection algorithm for all images.

Experiment was conducted in a controlled environment to acquire images with minimal interference. Challenges in acquisition and processing

So for this purpose the experimental setup looked like as shown below in figure 3.

Figure 3: Approximation to experimental setup used to take images of test object.

In figure 3 it could be seen that Camera is connected to computer via USB cable this is to make sure that all the images are taken without touching the camera so that all the acquired images are static, further improvement could have involved Micromachined accelerometers which can account for mechanical and optical interference [15] in this experiment only Light source used was variable i-e its intensity could be varied.

need for maintaining temperature of optical sensor otherwise with higher intensities generating enough power will require cryocooler systems to keep optical sensors stable during high-intensity illumination. [17]

Choice of incline as test object was made so that light intensity varies on plane of incline which its gradually increasing distance with light source at the back of this test object LUX sensor was placed to determine the value of light intensity. As light intensity was not used on extreme high intensity also optical sensor used was normal 16 Mega Pixel camera, therefore there was no

Algorithm being employed

Algorithm which was employed for finding variations in images being acquired comprises of RGB to Grey Image, High Pass Filter Application for Edge Detection, Edge Variation Detection Across approximately 30 on each left and right edge, figure 4 shows the flow chart of algorithm. All the work related to image filtering has been done using MATLAB as MATLAB-based image preprocessing improves edge detection and noise suppression. [22] [4]

Figure 4: Flow chart of algorithm applied for edge detecting and edge variation detection across number of images.

Figure 5 shows how image looks after application of high pass filter and 5a is image with grey scale 5b is image with left edges 5c is image with right edges and image 5b (extension) is image showing enlarged part

of the edge on which inner and outer edge boundary detection is used. Digital image correlation allows high-fidelity deformation and surface tracking. [23]

Figure 5: High pass filter and enlarged view of edge boundary detection. 5a: Image in grey scale. 5b: Left edge detected. 5c: Right edge detected. 5d: enlarged view of edge.

Edge detection works for inner and outer edges of the test object after applying high pass filter, flow chart related to inner edge detection is shown in figure 6.

Figure 6: Inner edge detection part of algorithm being employed

From objects which are polished/unpolished Aluminum and Steel i.e total of 4 test objects, for each of these 93 images are acquired each image is converted to grey scale high pass filters are applied for edge detection and after that for each of the right and left edge for all 4 test objects center points are found on these edges manually in one of the images and pixel coordinates of these center points which are about 30 are recorded.

Now for each of these center points values of cursor is checked as shown in figure 5d if pixel value is 255 then 1 is added in cursor's current x-axis position making it move to one side until pixel value is equal to 255. If pixel value is less than 255 then this value is recorded as value of inner boundary of the edge. This process is repeated for all the 30 center points coordinates found manually once all the values of inner edges are found data is stored in MS Excel file.

Figure 7: Outer Edge detection part of algorithm being employed

Outer edge detection works the same way as inner edge detection except for one thing that now 1 unit is subtracted from cursor's current position and in contrast to inner edge cursor now moves in opposite direction.

Results And Discussion

Once all the values for edges are recorded then for better analysis graphs are drawn to have a better

understanding of behavior of these two Material categorizations (Rough metal vs Polished) changes with light direction, intensity, and surface roughness [24], there are total number of 8 graphical results were obtained all of these are going to be discussed in this sections. Results of this study are divided in two parts Polished and Unpolished Aluminum and Steel

Figure 8: White light Unpolished Aluminum (Blue) and Steel (Red) x-axis: Light intensity in LUX, y-axis Pixel variations.

Figure 8 shows pixel variation response of unpolished Aluminum and Steel when subjected to varying light intensities of white light, graphs are best fit curves in order to compensate for any error during the recording of these observations, for steel it could be

seen that initially pixel variation is maximum but then gradually decreases for values around 250 LUX and onwards, peak pixel variation for steel is approximately around 5px and minimum value is around 2px from 300 to 350 LUX, for unpolished

Aluminum its peak is around 5px for 50 LUX and variation starts to decline from 150 LUX and onwards until 350 LUX and is around 3px.

From the graph it could be seen that pixel variation of unpolished steel is lesser than that of unpolished Aluminum this could be regarded as if image of

unpolished Aluminum and Steel is taken in same environment and light intensity varies with depth of object being imaged then steel will give a better result with lesser variations in image than aluminum for white light most probably this will be the case for dimensional analysis i.e 3d scanning objects.

Figure 9: Warm light Unpolished Aluminum (Blue) and Steel (Red) x-axis: Light intensity in LUX, y-axis Pixel variations.

Figure 9 shows pixel variations of aluminum and steel under the varying light intensity of warm light in graph it could be seen that pixel variation for unpolished aluminum is greater than that of unpolished steel, for aluminum it peaks at around 3px and then gradually decreases and falls to around 1px,

for steel it peaks at around 3.5px but then rapidly falls to 1px between 100 to 150 LUX and then lowest point is at around 0.5px at 300 LUX.

Therefore it could be deduced that for warm light unpolished Steel has lesser pixel variation as compared to unpolished Aluminum.

Figure 10: Red/Pinkish light Unpolished Aluminum (Blue) and Steel (Red) x-axis: Light intensity in LUX, y-axis Pixel variations.

Figure 10 shows graphical response of pixel variations against the light intensity variation on unpolished Aluminum and Steel from the graph it could be seen that Aluminum is having greater Pixel variation when compared to Steel pixel variation for Aluminum starts from 4.5px and drops down to 2px at 20 LUX then again rises and remains at around 4.5px between 40

to 70 LUX then drops 4px at 90LUX to around 0.5px, for steel variation in pixel is much lower starting from 1.5px then drops to around 0px at 20 LUX rises to around 3px remains at around 3px between 80 and 90 LUX then drops to 0px again.

From figure 10 it could be deduced that Unpolished Steel is having lesser variation when compared to

unpolished Aluminum under the influence of variable light intensity of red/pinkish light source.

Figure 11: Blue light Unpolished Aluminum (Blue) and Steel (Red) x-axis: Light intensity in LUX, y-axis Pixel variations.

Figure 11 is graphical response of pixel variation caused by varying light intensity of Blue light from figure 11 graphical response has slight difference between Aluminum and Steel but for most of the part

of the graph unpolished steel having lower values as compared to Aluminum. Maximum pixel variation is around 3.5px for both metals and minimum is zero at around 120 LUX.

Figure 12: White light Polished Aluminum (Blue) and Steel (Red) x-axis: Light intensity in LUX, y-axis Pixel variations.

Figure 12 shows response of pixel variation when Polished Aluminum and Steel were subjected to varying light intensity of white light from graph it could be seen that at around 50 LUX aluminum and steel both were at 7px Aluminum peaks at 9px at 100 LUX and Steel is around 6px then values for pixel variation drops for aluminum from 9px to around 6px

at 150 LUX and for steel it is at around 3px, values for aluminum then show some stability at around 6px and for steel it is between 3px and 2px. From figure 12 it could then be deduced that polished steel has lesser pixel variation as compared to polished aluminum.

Figure 13: Warm light Polished Aluminum (Blue) and Steel (Red) x-axis: Light intensity in LUX, y-axis Pixel variations.

Figure 13 is the graphical response of the pixel variation against the light intensity variation for warm light source, pixel variation for aluminum peaks at around 5px and same is the case for steel between 0 to 50 LUX then this value drops down to 3px for aluminum and below 1px for steel, for aluminum it rises to between 4px to 5px and for steel it rises to 2px, between 100 to 300 LUX Aluminum values are

between 4 and 5px whereas for steel between 100 to 250 LUX values ranges between 1px to 2px then rises to between 2px and 3px in between 250 and 300 LUX, after 300 LUX values for Aluminum falls to 2px and for steel it falls to nearly 0px.

So for warm light Polished steel is providing with better results in terms of pixel variation when compared to polished Aluminum.

Figure 14: Red/Pinkish light Polished Aluminum (Blue) and Steel (Red) x-axis: Light intensity in LUX, y-axis Pixel variations.

Figure 14: shows the response for Polished Aluminum and Steel for red/pinkish light source, maximum recorded pixel variation for polished steel is at around 7px in between 40 to 50 LUX which decreases to below 1px at around 90 LUX, for polished Aluminum maximum variation is around 5px between 40 and 50 LUX and this too decreases to below 1px at around 90 LUX.

From graphical responses in figure 14 it could be seen that polished Aluminum is having lesser pixel variation as compared to polished steel, so unlike white and warm light Aluminum is showing better response in comparison to steel for pixel variation when subjected to varying light intensity of red/pinkish light source.

Figure 15: Blue light Polished Aluminum (Blue) and Steel (Red) x-axis: Light intensity in LUX, y-axis Pixel variations.

Figure 15 shows graphical response for polished aluminum and steel when subjected to varying light intensities of blue light, in this graph it could be seen that pixel variation for polished steel is greater than that of polished aluminum for steel peak is at around 5px between 40 and 60 LUX and then decreases to 3px at around 60 then second peak for polished steel is at around 4px between 100 and 120 LUX and then rapid decreases to zero at around 140 LUX.

For polished Aluminum it peaks at around 4px at 40 LUX then decreases to 1px at around 100 LUX then second peak is around 3.5px at around 120 LUX and then decreases to zero at between 140 and 160 LUX. For blue light polished aluminum shows lesser pixel variation in comparison to polished steel.

There are total number of 8 graphical results obtained out of which 4 are given in results section of this paper remaining 4 will be discussed along with all the mentioned 4 in this section of the paper.

Materials used are Aluminum and Steel and in Polished and Unpolished conditions as was mentioned in materials and methods sections after all the 4 types of material being subjected to 4 different light sources we have finally obtained the summarized result which may allow us to determine two important factor which were dealt in this study

1. Which material (Aluminum/Steel) offer better image scanning with lesser pixel variation.
2. Which of the light sources are best suited for these materials when being scanned using imaging technology.

POLISHED				UNPOLISHED		
LIGHTS	G Px	L Px	AD Px	G Px	L Px	AD Px
White	ALUMINUM	STEEL	3 Px	ALUMINUM	STEEL	0.25 Px
Warm	ALUMINUM	STEEL	2 Px	ALUMINUM	STEEL	1 Px
Red	STEEL	ALUMINUM	1 Px	ALUMINUM	STEEL	1.5 Px
Blue	STEEL	ALUMINUM	0.75 Px	ALUMINUM	STEEL	0.5 Px

G Px = Greater Pixel Change L Px = Lesser Pixel Change AD Px = Average Difference of Pixel

Figure 16: Comparative summary of Aluminum Steel and 4 light sources

Figure 16 summarizes the result from these 8 experiments in a concise manner, conclusion will be based on the results obtained and summarized in this figure 16, discussion will be broken down in two parts 1st part will be of polished materials and 2nd part will be of unpolished materials.

Polished Aluminum and Steel:

in accordance with figure 16 it could be seen that between polished Aluminum and Steel for warm and white light Aluminum has greater pixel variations but for blue and red/pinkish light Steel has greater pixel variation.

AD Px is average difference of pixels between two materials with respect to light they are subjected in, for white and warm light it is 3px and 2px respectively with Aluminum having greater pixel variations, for red and blue light it is 1px and 0.75px with Steel having greater pixel variations

Unpolished Aluminum and Steel:

in figure 16 it could be seen that for all of the 4 light sources i.e white, warm, red/pinkish and blue steel is having lesser pixel variation as compared to Aluminum.

Average difference of pixels between materials which is AD Px is 0.25px, 1px, 1.5px and 0.5px for white, warm, red/pinkish and blue light sources.

Conclusion

In this study 4 different light sources are used along with 4 different materials so conclusion will be based on two major parts of 1 of the part of the conclusion will comprise of behavior of the material when subjected to different lights and their varying light intensities. Another conclusion will be made regarding the light sources which are used in this study.

Polished Aluminum and Steel:

From figure 16 it is very clearly evident that steel has the best response when being imaged, pixel variation from steel are only greater in the case when it was Polished and subjected to Red and Blue light for remaining two light sources on polished steel it showed lesser pixel variations. Even when subjected to red/pinkish and blue light source average difference in pixel is 1px for red light and 0.75px for blue light source whereas for Polished Aluminum this 3px and 2px for white and warm light respectively.

Unpolished Aluminum and Steel:

Again from figure 16 for unpolished materials it could be seen that Steel has lesser pixel variations, but also for unpolished aluminum and steel average difference of pixels is lesser but for all 4 light sources Steel shows better response when subjected to changing light intensities and being imaged.

So for 3D scanning using images and especially for dimensional analysis steel becomes better candidate than Aluminum as with lesser changes in pixel while being imaged will cause better result to be acquired with minimal variations and errors.

Now for the comparison of light sources which were being used in this study, values of AD Px could be used for better comparison of sources. For this again figure 16 will be referred

Polished Aluminum and Steel:

AD Px for 4 light which are white, warm, red/pinkish and blue sources are as follows 3px, 2px, 1px and 0.75px respectively, it is quite clear that minimal value is that of blue light source when shone on Polished Aluminum and Steel.

Unpolished Aluminum and Steel:

AD Px for the light sources are follows for white, warm, red/pinkish and blue light source 0.25px, 1px, 1.5px and 0.5px respectively, from here it could be seen that value of white light is minimal which is 0.25px but for polished material white light has a value of 3px change for white light is 2.75px between Polished and unpolished material, whereas for blue light this change is of 0.25px which is quite negligible. So from analysis of light sources it could be deduced that if a 3d scanning is to be done using a single light source then that light source should emit blue light as this shows the better result for all 4 materials.

With different material and light sources better results could have been possible like, Black aluminum created via femtosecond lasers has enhanced anti-reflective properties [10] for polished material selective laser melting creates highly reflective mirror-like metal surfaces [20], combination of these two could have provided great diversity in materials being used if Laser were to be used instead of diffused light source then surface roughness and reflectivity vary greatly with femtosecond laser scan frequency [12] and Laser speckle contrast analysis yields fast surface roughness profiles [21] other digital new methods could be employed like machine learning could be used to predict steel surface roughness from reflected laser angle data. [19].

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